

INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE TEMPERATURE ON SILKWORM SEED REVIVAL

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Annotation: The article provides information on the recovery rate of imported silkworm seeds, the duration, amount and other indicators of the recovery of local seeds. It has been proved that the seeds produced in our country do not lag behind imported seeds in terms of incubation process and worm recovery rates, and even some of them are slightly higher.

Keywords: cocoon, mulberry, mushroom, environment, confusion, party, god, gender.

Introduction. Today, the demand for cocoons, natural silk and silk fabrics in the world market is growing day by day. At present, mulberry silkworm eggs are produced in more than 20 countries where silk production is developed, and 14.5 million silkworm eggs are produced. box People's Republic of China, 5.0 million. box India, 300,000 boxes Uzbekistan and the remaining 3.2 million. box falls to the share of other states. " Uzbekistan is the third largest cocoon producer in the world, producing an average of 59.0 kg of cocoons per box of silkworm seeds. The geographical location of Uzbekistan is currently a favorable ecological zone for the cultivation of silkworms, and more than 380-400 thousand boxes of silkworms are cared for annually.

Research is being carried out around the world to create breeds and hybrids of mulberry silkworms adapted to the climatic conditions of different regions and to introduce new innovative agro-technologies in silkworm breeding. In this regard, taking into account global climate change, the creation of breeds and hybrids of mulberry silkworms adapted to rapidly changing and optimal climatic conditions,

the development of new intensive technologies for their care and the introduction of foreign breeds and hybrids are of great scientific and practical importance.

In our country, certain results are being achieved in the creation of local breeds and hybrids in accordance with the specific climatic conditions. However, insufficient attention is paid to the development and scientific substantiation of optimal care agro-technologies aimed at adapting imported mulberry silkworm breeds to the conditions of Uzbekistan, increasing their capacity in terms of cocoon yield, variety and technological characteristics.

Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-2856 of March 29, 2017 "On measures to organize the activities of the Association" Uzbekpaksanoat "and No. PD-3616 of March 20, 2018" On additional measures for further development of the silk industry " Extensive testing of worm selection achievements, development of primary breeding of mulberry silkworm breeds and hybrids, taking into account the natural climatic conditions of the regions, It is planned to expand the export potential of the silk industry by creating advanced breeds and hybrids that meet international standards through the development of advanced scientific developments and intensive agro-technologies, increasing the production of local silkworms and cocoons, improving their quality.

In order to eliminate these shortcomings and speed up the implementation of government decisions, it is necessary to identify a number of measures in cooperation with farms and enterprises to accelerate the implementation of scientific innovations. In order to positively address these issues, it is important to determine the amount of revived seeds imported from abroad. Therefore, we conducted our research to identify this issue and apply it in production.

1-table

The order and amount of worms hatching from 29 g (one box) of seeds in the incubator (2022 year).

The day the worm came out of the seed	Of revived seed		The amount of live worm, gr
	Quantity,gr	In%	
Informant worms	0,14	0,5	0,1
Numerous (gross) emergence of worms:			
The first day	13,90	48	9,74
The second day	12,20	42	8,52
On the third day	2,76	9,5	1,94
General	29	100	20,3

The research work was incubated using the recommended constant temperature method for silkworm seed wrapped in white cocoons, and the

number of live worms and the number of non-live seeds per day were determined. Initially the messenger worms were then calculated as the percentage of worms revived over 4 days.

The experiments were conducted at the Silk Research Institute. The data obtained from the studies are presented in Table 1 below.

2-table

Determining the amount of revitalization of silkworm seeds (2022 year)

Options	Incubation period, days	Egg hatching,%				Total live worms,%	Inactive seeds,%	
		Informant worms	1 - day	2 - day	3 - day			4 - day
Options -1	10	0,5	50	43	3	-	96,5	3,5
Options -2	10	1,5	48,5	40	6	-	96,0	4,0
Options -3	11	1,5	44	43	7	-	95,5	4,5

The figures in the table show that the seeds produced in our country do not lag behind, even slightly superior to imported seeds in terms of their revival (incubation) period, quantity (percentage) and other indicators. For example, if the incubation period was the same as with the seed (10 days), the total number of live worms was 1% higher than the other seed if it was revived the day before.

Figure 1. Revitalization of silkworm breed and hybrid seeds in the laboratory.

Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that the mulberry silkworm breeds imported from abroad have indeed shown that their biological and productivity indicators are higher than our domestic silkworms..

References:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2017 No PD-2856 "On measures to organize the activities of the Uzbekpaksanoat Association." - Tashkent, 2017. 1-5-p.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 20, 2018 No PP-3616 "On additional measures for further development of the silk industry." - Tashkent, 2018. 1-4-p.4.
3. Axmedov.N.A Revitalization of silkworm seeds. // Tashkent, 1992y. P. 6-7.
4. Axmedov.N.A Influence of the period of temporary cessation of embryonic development on silkworm seed germination during silkworm seed revival. // Silk. –Tashkent, 1998. - №2.- P.11-12.
5. Axmedov.N.A. Structure of mulberry silkworm eggs. Silk–Tashkent, 1998. - №3.- P. 18-19.
6. Axmedov.N.A. Effect of contrast temperature and humidity on silkworm seed regeneration. Silk–Tashkent, 1998. - №4.- P. 22-23.

